

Impact of the development and deployment of software on energy consumption: findings and recommendations

Part of the UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project

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This report presents our methodology, findings and recommendations for a series of interviews and a survey on the impact of the development and deployment of software on energy consumption. We present recommendations on minimising full lifecycle emissions of institutional facilities and on optimising code and reducing coding mistakes. In summary, these involve introduction of policies at institutional level, providing support in the form of experts in green software engineering and energy efficient software design, and provide adequate training for researchers as well as experts.

1 Introduction

One of the aims of the Glasgow University Consortium Project (part of the UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project) was to investigate impact of the development and deployment of software on emissions, i.e. how much can be saved by using different development practices, programming languages, programming frameworks, compilers and runtime systems, etc¹.

The instruments for this research were a series of interviews with domain experts, mostly in domains under EPSRC remit, and a questionnaire, distributed across UKRI via the main project.

2 Interviews

The two main motivators for conducting interviews were to gather more information to improve the design of the survey (covered in the survey section), and to provide context and explanations for the eventual results. Via a literature review, we established which practices can lead to greater energy efficiency. In the interviews, we aimed to discover the underlying cultural and practical factors which lead to the adoption or lack of adoption of these practices. That is, researchers who regularly use digital research infrastructure possess knowledge and experiences that can inform potential approaches for increasing the adoption of best practices.

¹The other aim, reported separately, was to investigate the relative importance of emissions resulting from UKRI funded research but not directly attributable to facilities, e.g. desktop machines, data movement to and from facilities and storage, emissions from UKRI-founded equipment that are not facilities.

2.1 Interview aims and design

As the main aims of the interviews was to gather information and to explore sentiments and opinions around the possible interventions or practices which could arise from the project, the interview was loosely structured around the use of facilities, software engineering practices, hardware in use by researchers, and limitations/pressures facing researchers who do digital research.

The approach to the interviews was mainly based on 4 qualitative analysis methodologies: start with a tree of keywords/topics from exploration, allow the interviewees to opine around the given questions where possible (but not for too long), update the tree with lessons learned from each interview, and avoid bias in how questions are phrased or in their intonation when stated.

The initial tree in this case was derived from the first draft of the questionnaire, but interviewees were asked to expand on their answers where possible, and they were allowed to veer off track for a short amount of time. From each interview to the next, more sub-questions would be formed (and sometimes wholly new topics would be brought on), making the next interviews question those same sentiments/opinions/facts if they were deemed pertinent.

We started by interviewing computing scientists in different sub-fields, then branched out to scientists in different fields. Notes were taken during each interview and afterwards coded and summarised.

2.2 Interview Results

2.2.1 Use of local facilities and devices

Almost all researchers we interviewed had access to a local cluster to use for their research. None of these clusters required checks for software correctness or optimisation before use. Booking time on a cluster was done via calendar booking or on a first come, first served basis.

We got information on cluster utilisation for 3 clusters - 2 CPU-based clusters and 1 GPU-based cluster. For the CPU-based clusters, we got access to the booking calendar used to allocate resources on the cluster. For both of these clusters, utilisation was in the 0-10% range. That is, for most days, there would not be any experiments running on the cluster. The interviewees in these cases did not know whether there were any power saving measures in place for the machines in this cluster. The GPU-based cluster had a utilisation in the 50-70% range based on an on-the-spot utilisation check and interviewee recall. The interviewee had no knowledge of power saving measures for this cluster, but noted it may not make a notable difference as the GPUs draw almost no power when idling compared to power under load.

From one interview, we observed a practice of squatting to ensure the resources would be available to the researcher. That is, they would allocate resources with their first come, first served system, then have a Jupyter notebook instance running on GPUs to ensure they were ready when they needed them. Once they "let go" of their allocated resources, someone else might allocate them. It was considered normal that 15-20 GPUs out of 60 to be in this state, drawing ~25 W out of the 350 W maximum. This would be an easy target for energy saving measures, as better scheduling practices could save the equivalent of 1-2 GPUs running at 100% in this instance. One factor driving the first come, first served booking practice is the uncertainty around the expected runtime of Machine Learning (ML) models. If a certain timeframe was booked in advance, but the model had not finished running, either the researcher has to terminate early and lose their results, or the other researcher would have to wait an undetermined amount of time before running their own model. One factor driving the high occupancy is the lack of hardware for doing test runs on smaller samples. That is, to test whether their model was working correctly, they must allocate resources on the cluster,

occupy the resource until they are ready to run their software, then run their model when ready.

Users of the CPU-based clusters argued that the clusters were an important stepping stone for testing software before running on national facilities. That is, they would use the local clusters to verify whether their software would scale (run faster/not slow down) when extended to use multiple compute nodes. One interviewee stated that they would need more powerful workstations rather than laptops for their daily work, leading to less centralisation of computation.

One GPU cluster user noted that the easy access to the cluster was a key incentive for them to work for our university, as they could carry out their research at a faster pace.

Interviewees from multiple schools stated that they have access to and make use of various workstations to run experiments or small scale trials. In several cases, these workstations included a GPU as an accelerator. Researchers from 2 schools noted that they primarily use these workstations or servers for their work, and one of them would sometimes scale their work to run on regional or national facilities. Runtimes for software on these workstations could be hours, days, weeks, or months, and they are typically always powered on. One researcher also noted that the power policy of this workstation was 'always on'. A researcher primarily using a GPU cluster had also purchased a GPU workstation for their home (with their own money) so that they could run small scale experiments without waiting for cluster availability.

Most researchers would use a laptop for their daily work, while others used desktops. One interviewee noted desktops around their office would usually be powered on.

2.2.2 Optimisations practices

Overall, effort is not put toward optimising research software. We heard from many researchers that potential optimisations are sometimes clearly apparent, and from a few researchers that they would not know how to optimise their software. A sentiment among almost all interviewees was that effort is not put toward optimisation because it would hinder their work in some way. They have the option to run their software as-is on workstations and some facilities while they continue to do their work, so there are only downsides for them to take the time to work on optimisation. However, they would make use of optimised libraries/modules if they learn that they can get their results quicker by doing so.

Two potential solutions were suggested to work around the above sentiment preventing researchers from optimising their software. One interviewee noted that some code would often be repeated within their group, so one of their colleagues had put in the work to create a software library to handle these common tasks, and this library had been optimised so that the work could be done quickly. Identifying these commonalities and concentrating effort toward optimising such shared resources was more amenable to this researcher.

We also inquired about their perception toward working with Research Software Engineers (RSEs). This measure was largely welcomed, as the researchers would take what help they could get with their coding, as long as the work could be done within a certain timeframe individual to each researcher. In many cases, their software would finish running overnight. They would continue working with their results in hand the next day, so even if an RSE was reviewing their software, they would run the unreviewed version if the wait is too long. We also noted a general perception that RSEs would need to be involved in- or part of the project to be helpful, as some researchers view their work as too complicated for their software to be reviewed purely from a computing perspective.

We had one interviewee outside of computing science who stated they had access to help from a knowledgeable colleague who would sometimes create efficient modules for common computing tasks within their team. They had recently added an RSE to their group, but had

not yet come to the point of utilising them. Another interviewee had an RSE as part of their project grant for 2 days a week, but they would usually not do their work, and were not held accountable to their project milestones.

Optimisations are not a requirement for running software on any local facilities or standalone workstations for any interviewees or their colleagues. Given that sentiment toward spending time optimising their software was overall negative, such requirements would likely be unwelcome among researchers.

We did come across an energy saving form of optimisation which we did not include in the survey: intermediate result re-use. In some workflows, a large amount of data may be produced in one step of the computation which will be used as an input to another step.

2.2.3 Unusable results

Everyone we interviewed would produce bugs or flaws in their on a somewhat regular basis. This could arise from mistakes made while programming, or conceptual errors made while developing the model before any programming had started. Running their experiment on a small sample was by far the most common way of checking for these flaws. This is commonly known as manual testing, and is often only form of testing for ML/AI codes. However, there are still automated tests which can be applied to parts of the software which do not pass through AI.

None of the interviewed researchers would automate their testing with unit testing or integration testing. The sentiment around this is the same as in the previous subsection: creating the tests was seen as time and effort researchers could not or would not commit. However, the prospect of having RSEs who could create these automated tests was viewed positively.

Code reviews were also not an observed practice. The sentiment was the same as with automated testing: taking the time to understand and predict the behaviour of a colleague's code was seen as too time-consuming. Having this work done by an RSE was viewed favourably, but would need to be completed within hours or up to one day.

Some interviewees stated that errors would sometimes lie in the model they developed before they started programming, but there was no indication the researchers were checking each other's models for mistakes.

2.3 Interviews Conclusions

2.3.1 Use of local facilities and devices

From these interviews we can conclude that there are clear needs for institutional clusters and communal workstations/servers. The main reason for such facilities is to lower the barrier to access by offering flexibility.

The commonly observed model of first-come first-serve access to such resources is not a good policy in terms of energy efficiency because it can lead to squatting, i.e. occupying compute resources as a way to claim them; and it also does not encourage planning experiments carefully, leading to unnecessary long experiments.

However, it is clear that a too restrictive regime would lead some researchers to invest in additional resources or look for resources elsewhere, which would negate any energy savings.

The observed low utilisation of local clusters can't be generalised, but to optimise while-life-cycle emissions, average load should be a factor to determine the replacement cycles of the hardware.

2.3.2 Optimisation practices and Unusable results

A clear conclusion from the questions relating to optimisation, debugging and testing is that this is not mainly a technical issue, and so can't be resolved purely by training the researchers. The reasons for not optimising code is that researchers feel it is not worth their time. So it is better to invest in RSEs to optimise the code.

A similar issue is at play for unit testing and integration testing, and code and model reviews: even though researchers recognise that they have to rerun experiments on a somewhat regular basis (either because of mistakes in the conceptual model or due to bugs), they are unwilling to adopt better software engineering practices because essentially they see it was a waste of time. Whereas assessing of code was optimised is difficult, assessing if proper software engineering practices were followed is easy. Therefore, this issue could be addressed through sufficient incentivisation (i.e make it a requirement), in particular for experiments on institutional or regional clusters or UKRI facilities. This would need to be combined either with RSE support or researcher training.

3 Survey

3.1 Survey aims and design

During our literature review, we uncovered several avenues for energy savings in research code. Another team within the consortium was working on covering major digital research facilities, so we look at the impact of computing outside of such facilities. According to our preliminary calculations, institution/school level facilities, and even personal computing hardware are responsible for a significant amount of energy consumption and resulting emissions associated with UKRI funded digital research infrastructure. We therefore set out to map the facilities and personal hardware in use within institutions, starting with our own school, and the facilities in use within our own university. We also created a questionnaire aimed at digital research practices, and interviewed a series of researchers at our own university.

3.2 The survey

3.2.1 Filtering for researchers who run digital experiments

Most of the questions in the survey ask about software development practices, so we needed a clear way to separate the coders from the non-coders. To do this, we posed the following 2 questions, which could be answered 'Yes', 'No', or 'Not sure':

- Have you written/modified code to investigate hypotheses/experiments as part of your research? (For instance, for producing data visualisation, processing data, or testing a model)
- Have you run existing software to investigate hypotheses/experiments as part of your research? (For instance, for producing data visualisation, processing data, or testing a model)

3.2.2 Institutional computing facilities

As part of our objectives is to survey institutional level facilities which are not mapped or detailed anywhere we could find, we included a section to capture details about the respondents local facilities.

A filter question to determine whether the respondent was a user of the facility ('Yes', 'No', or 'Not sure'):

- Have you run your software on a computing cluster or computation node? (For instance, a set of computers or a computer with a set of accelerators (GPUs))

To get a better picture of the specifications of non-UKRI-managed facilities (long text response):

- If readily available, what are the specifications of the cluster(s)/node(s) (e.g. number of nodes, CPU details, RAM, storage)?

It's important to determine if the facility is being used or run efficiently. We have noted some facilities within our own school were at very low occupancy, but it was not known whether the cluster would partially or wholly shut down during long periods of inactivity. If this was a common practice, major savings could potentially be found by changing this practice, which would be a one-off action.

(Multiple-choice question, 0%-100% (10% intervals), 'Not sure', or 'Other' - a write-in choice):

- What is the occupancy (percentage of time at which the facility is at 100% usage) of the cluster(s)/node(s)? (A rough estimate is fine, and this would include usage by other users. For nationwide supercomputing services, like ARCHER, you can skip this and the next 2 questions)

About the timeframe for the answer to the last question (short text answer):

- What is the timeframe for the above occupancy answer?

About power saving measures in place (long text answer):

- Does the facility have any power saving measures? (Such as powering down/going to sleep when not in use or use of dynamic frequency/voltage scaling)

With a sufficient response rate, we could compare time spent running software on the given hardware against the practices covered later in the survey.

About estimating the amount of time their software has run on the above hardware to the closest order of magnitude (hours/days/weeks/months/years). Magnitudes only as more precise estimates would be hard to work out.

- Cumulatively, for how long have you been running your software on the cluster(s)/node(s)? (In other words, how long has all the listed hardware spent running your software combined? Answers are on the closest order of magnitude)

3.2.3 Various computing devices

During our interviews, we came across a wide range of computing devices in use by researchers which would not classify as a 'facility'. We wanted to capture details of such devices for our estimates of power consumption. This would include personal devices, and specialised workstations

About the personal devices ('Laptop without extra monitor', 'Laptop with extra monitor', 'Desktop', 'Tablet', or 'Other' - a write-in option):

- What personal computing devices do you use as part of your research?

About the specification of these devices (long text answer):

- If readily available, what are the specifications (e.g. CPU, RAM, disk) or the model of the computer?

About specialised workstations which may be shared within some teams or schools (long text answer):

- If you have access to a workstation to run research code other than the above, but which could not be called 'a facility' (e.g. special accelerators, non-standard configuration, a high-powered shared workstation), please describe it here

If these workstations had any power saving measures (long text answer):

- Does the standalone computer have any power saving measures? (such as powering down/going to sleep when not in use or use of dynamic frequency/voltage scaling)

About the researchers' cumulative runtime on these workstations to the closest order of magnitude (hours/days/weeks/months/years). Orders of magnitude because closer estimates are hard to produce.

- Cumulatively, for how long have you been running your software on the standalone computers? (on the order of)

3.2.4 Software efficiency

In the literature review, we explored several practices and methodologies which could reduce the energy consumption of software. Choices of languages and/or libraries can affect the energy efficiency of the software, along with optimisations which affect runtime. Even parallelising software (as long as it's on a single node) can increase energy efficiency.

The programming language used to create software will have an effect on the software's energy efficiency. An algorithm implemented in Python or Matlab may be many times less efficient than one implemented in C/C++, Java, or Rust.

(Short text answer so that respondents could fill in all the languages they frequently use).

- Which language(s) did you primarily use to create this software? (for instance, Python, Matlab, R, C/C++, Java)

A caveat to the above point on programming languages is that less efficient languages like Python give access to libraries with highly optimised routines written in more efficient languages. A researcher may write a piece of code in Python to perform calculations almost entirely using NumPy/SciPy. In that case, most of the runtime of that software is spent executing efficient code, despite the language not being very efficient. However, not all libraries are necessarily efficient.

About the most used libraries (long text answer):

- Which (if any) libraries/tools do you primarily use to create this software? (for instance, Numpy, Tensorflow, Pandas)

To open up the optimisation specific questions, we asked about respondent perception about the energy efficiency of their software. If research code is already highly optimised, there would not be much room for recommendations in this area. We asked about perception explicitly rather than the objective case as that would be very difficult for most respondents to gauge (on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Not optimised' and 5 being 'Highly optimised'):

- How optimised do you think the software you have run on clusters/nodes is in terms of energy efficiency?

How many researchers already optimise their own software (in part to get an overview of existing practice, and to tie in with later questions; 'Yes'/'No' question):

- Do you optimise the software yourself?

If researchers have support for their computing needs. During our interviews, we had some subjects with support from knowledgeable colleagues, and others who had research software engineers they could call on.

(Multiple choice question, options: 'Help from a computing specialist', 'Help from a knowledgeable colleague', 'No help', 'Other' - a write-in option):

- Do you have access to help to optimise the software you run on clusters/nodes?

During our interviews, we also noted a sentiment toward the timeliness for support needed to be practical being quite tight, so if this remained the case among researchers more generally (long text answer):

- How quickly do you need to have access to help for it to be useful? (for instance, so that it would be implemented before you run the software)

To make recommendations about implementing practices toward optimisation of research software, we need to know which practices are already in place.

How researchers optimise their software (multiple-choice question, 'Profiling', 'Parallelisation', 'Compiler optimisation options', 'Highly efficient algorithms', and 'Other' - a write-in option):

- How was your software optimised?

To gauge how well each of these optimisation practices are pursued (on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Not confident' and 5 being 'Highly confident'):

- How confident are you in the parallel efficiency of your software?
- How confident are you in the compiler optimisations of your software?
- How confident are you in the efficiency of the algorithm(s) you've implemented?

Whether optimisations are required for running software on local facilities. If there is a lack of optimisations, this could be recommended as a potential measure for forcing efficient software development. ('Yes', 'No', 'Not sure', or 'Other' - a write-in option):

- Are you required to optimise the software before it is allowed to be run on the cluster/node?

When researchers are starting out on a project that requires them to write research software, finding the right algorithm is often a starting point. There are often multiple choices for algorithms and data structures for any specific task.

About criteria are used for selecting algorithms and data structures (long text answer in both cases):

- What are the main criteria you consider when selecting algorithms for your software? (for instance, high precision, short runtime, ease of implementation)
- What are the main criteria you consider when selecting data structures for your software? (for instance, high precision, short runtime, ease of implementation)

3.2.5 Unusable results

Mistakes are an inevitable part of writing software. They will happen sometimes, but how frequently they do happen is something developers can manage. In professional software engineering, practices such as unit testing, integration testing, and code reviews are in place to catch them as often as possible. If a lot of CPU time is being spent on running software which will not yield usable results, there could be energy savings to be made by applying software engineering practices.

We wanted to build an overview of how frequent bugs and flaws are in the field. With enough responses, we can also compare the frequency of bugs with the responses to the questions below. (on a scale of 1-5, with 1 being 'Never' and 5 being 'All the time'):

- How often do you run software on a cluster/node you later discovered contained a bug or other flaw which led to a result that wholly or partially could not be used?

To make recommendations for best practices, we need to know what is already implemented in the field. We predefined the response options as there are not that many practices: 'Code reviews', 'Unit testing', 'Integration testing', 'Having your model reviewed', 'Run software on smaller samples', 'None', and 'Other' - a write-in option.

- Which of the following procedures do you have to ensure software is correct before running it on a cluster/node?

To measure the perceived effectiveness of these practices, we also asked directly how effective they are at catching mistakes (on a scale of 1-5, with 1 being 'Never' and 5 being 'Always'):

- Do these procedures prevent results that cannot be used?

If these practices are required before running software on facilities and compute nodes to ('Yes', 'No', 'Not sure', or 'Other' - a write-in option):

- Are you required to perform these procedures before the software is allowed to be run on the cluster/node?

Do researchers have support to help with software engineering practices? If they currently have no help, recommendations on providing that help could be argued ('A computing expert', 'A knowledgeable colleague', 'No help', and 'Other' - a write-in option):

- Do you have access to a computing specialist who can review your code for bugs?

During our interviews, we picked up some sentiment toward the timeliness of such reviews. To prevent researchers from running the code without review, the review would have to be completed within a couple hours in some cases. So, we wished to get a distribution to show how quick the turnaround of the reviews had to be to be useful in most cases ('Within an hour', 'Within hours', 'Within days', and 'Other' - a write-in option):

- How quick would those reviews have to be in order to be useful to you?

We had also gotten feedback that research software engineers would not be very useful in some cases, unless they were part of the team for the project. The rationale for this was that the intent and structure of the software would be too hard to get into in a short amount of time ('Yes', 'No', 'Not sure', or 'Other' - a write-in option):

- Do you think the computing specialist would have to be part of your project for their input to be useful?

To catch anything we might have missed, we included a long text response catch-all at the end of the survey:

- If you have any other details you think we should know, but did not cover in this questionnaire, please share them here.

4 Survey results

4.1 Filtering for researchers who run digital experiments

The scope of our research is mostly limited to digital experiments either written (programmed), modified, or parameterised by researchers, and then run on computers. Here, parameterised means no changes to code were made by the researcher, but they still deploy software with custom parameters. Due to this, most of the questions we asked are only relevant to this group

4.2 Institutional computing facilities

In this section, we cover whether researchers use institutional facilities, what those facilities are, how much those facilities are used, and whether any power saving measures are in place.

4.2.1 Use of compute facilities

Figure 1: Have you run your software on a computing cluster or computation node? (For instance, a set of computers or a computer with a set of accelerators (GPUs))

Roughly half of the respondents said they had run their software on either clusters or individual compute nodes. However, from the detailed analysis, three of these facilities are clearly large-scale UKRI facilities rather than institutional ones. Because of the small number of respondents, this does not allow us to draw any conclusions on how widespread the use of institutional facilities is.

4.2.2 Compute occupancy

We received 7 responses on the occupancy of compute responses. 4 of these were 'Not sure' and the remaining 3 were '90%'. Of the 3 certain responses, all had references national or regional level computing facilities. The 3 positive responses also responded that the timeframe for this occupancy was several years.

When collecting information about our local compute facilities, we observed much lower occupancies. For instance, within our own school, 2 CPU-based clusters were in the 0%-15% occupancy range, and a highly used GPU-based cluster was in the 50%-70% range. Therefore we don't draw conclusions from these responses.

7 responses

Figure 2: What is the occupancy (percentage of time at which the facility is at 100% usage) of the cluster(s)/node(s)? (A rough estimate is fine, and this would include usage by other users)

4.2.3 Power saving measures

3 respondents were aware that their computing facility employed power saving measures. These were their responses in question:

- Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS)
- Powering down + OS performance profiles
- On-site renewable energy sources, ground water cooling, re-use of heat

It is not possible to draw conclusions from this question. In our interviews, we found that primary users of the facilities do not necessarily know this either.

DVFS is common in modern hardware and should be enabled by default, so there is nothing actionable there. However, powering down devices could save a lot of energy where occupancy is very low.

4.2.4 Total software runtime

In this question, we were aiming to compare the total time a researcher's code has been running on the hardware they specified against the practices we asked about later in the survey. However, due to the low volume of responses, we cannot draw such conclusions with the limited data. What we can show is that we have responses from a wide range of experience in digital research.

5 responses

Figure 3: Cumulatively, for how long have you been running your software on the cluster(s)/node(s)? (In other words, how long has all the listed hardware spent running your software combined? Answers are on the closest order of magnitude)

4.3 Various computing devices

In this section, we try to cover the computing hardware that does not classify as a facility. This covers what researchers are using for their daily work, to what specialised computing machines they might have available to them locally.

4.3.1 Personal computing devices

Out of the 11 users with laptops+monitor, 2 of them also used desktops, 1 of them also had a tablet, and 1 of them also ticked 'laptop without extra monitor'. Overall, this is comparable with our local inventory of personal devices in the school.

With a much larger number of respondents, this question could be used to create an estimate for the power consumption of researchers personal devices, and the potential savings of moving from desktops to laptops and offloading compute-heavy tasks to centralised services.

Figure 4: What personal computing devices do you use as part of your research?

Hardware descriptions from the above responses:

- at least 16GB RAM on a laptop (nowadays 32GB), at least 64GB on a desktop
- XPS13 laptop (Intel Core i5/i7, between 8 and 32 GB RAM)
- "Processor 11th Gen Intel Core(i7-1185G7 @ 3.00GHz, 2995 Mhz, 4 Core(s), 16 GB RAM, 500 GB SSD – Microsoft Surface Pro 8"
- Dell Optiplex 5000, Intel Core i7-12700K, 32GB RAM
- 2.3 GHz Quad-Core Intel Core i7, 32 GB 3733 MHz LPDDR4X 1TB
- 16GB RAM
- "8-core CPU with 6 performance cores and 2 efficiency cores 14-core GPU, 16GB unified memory"
- Processor - 2.8 GHz Intel Core i7, Memory - 16 GB 1600 MHz DDR3
- Mac Studio, Apple M1 Max, 32 GB Memory
- Apple M1 Pro, 16 GB RAM

Most respondents (7/11) had 16 GB RAM, 4 had 32 GB RAM; most CPUs were Intel Core i7 (5/7); 2 were Arm; CPU clock speeds between 2 and 4 GHz. All this is in line with our own inventory.

4.3.2 Specialised, communal workstations

We wanted to create an overview of auxiliary hardware available to researchers. Having access to these workstations can work as an intermediary step when preparing to run software on a cluster, but their function could also be offloaded to centralised computing services. Centralised services could make more efficient use of the hardware (embodied carbon), set up more efficient cooling infrastructure, and potentially use on-site renewable energy generation. These options would be very difficult to arrange or justify for standalone workstations.

- Question: If you have access to a workstation to run research code other than the above, but which could not be called 'a facility' (e.g. special accelerators, non-standard configuration, a high-powered shared workstation), please describe it here

Results: 5 responses

- We have a mix of all, from a single workstation with FPGA and 100G NIC, to a rack full of GPU, DPU, FPGA, 100G NIC, programmable switches, etc.
- Yes, a research group server with 16 cores (not sure about the other specification as I can no longer access it).
- 4 GPU workstation, high end NVIDIA GPUs, AMD processor 4 TB storage 64GB RAM
- No (2 responses)

The first response is from an HPC code expert. Among the respondents who listed the above specifications, the mix of hardware answered 'yes', the group server answered 'not sure', and the GPU workstation answered that it goes to sleep/powers off. 3 respondents who did not list hardware also responded with 2 'yes' and 1 'yes, suspend when not in use'.

The overall conclusion is that most researchers do not use workstations with accelerators.

- To get an estimate for the amount of processing performed by these standalone machines, we also asked about the cumulative runtime of software.

This question turned out to be ambiguous as to whether we were asking about the time software has been running on standalone machines, or about the time the researcher has been using this practice. Combined with the even spread of responses, no clear conclusions can be drawn.

10 responses

Figure 5: Cumulatively, for how long have you been running your software on the standalone computers? (on the order of)

4.4 Software efficiency

4.4.1 Languages and libraries

From our literature review, we found that that languages may differ greatly in their runtime and energy efficiency. Furthermore, some libraries/modules may be more optimised than others, which would affect energy efficiency. For instance, code written in Python could be quite inefficient, but if most of the work being done is code from the NumPy library, the solution is likely efficient overall as much of the work is actually done by C/C++ code.

Question 1: Which language(s) did you primarily use to create this software? (for instance, Python, Matlab, R, C/C++, Java)

Question 2: Which (if any) libraries/tools do you primarily use to create this software? (for instance, Numpy, Tensorflow, Pandas)

Of the 10 responses, 6 used Python, 2 used Matlab, 2 use R, 4 used C/C++, 1 C#. All Python users used high-performance libraries of some kind: 4 NumPy, 2 SciPy, 1 PyBaMM, 1 PyTorch, 1 Iris, 1 Sire.

4.4.2 Optimisation practices, support, and confidence

To discover which practices might be useful to implement on the ground, we wanted a better picture of optimisation practices currently in use. In our interviews, we noted that researchers would do some optimisation themselves if they could do it in a very short amount of time, or if the runtime of their software was so long that they needed optimisation to get the results back quicker.

- We asked the researchers whether they optimise the software they produce. This can give a sense for how common this is in the field, and allows us to filter other questions in the questionnaire according to this response.

Figure 6: Do you optimise the software yourself?

Figure 6 shows the responses are evenly divided. Note that 1 of the 'no' responses is from a researcher who do not write their own code. Correlating this with the previous questions, we can conclude that on the whole, users of Python, R and Matlab do not optimise their code; users of C/C++/C# optimise their code.

- We wanted to know which practices researchers employed for their software in the field, so we asked for this directly with preset options, but also allowing write-ins in case we missed something.

7 responses

Figure 7: How was your software optimised?

The bottom two are write-in responses. "The secret sauce ..." is from a respondent who is an HPC code optimisation expert. The "No help" is from a respondent who do not write software as part of their research. Taking the above into account, 7 out of the 10 respondents who write research software gave answers for how they did so. Correlating with the language use, we conclude that these practices are common for respondents who used C/C++/C# but not for users of Python/R/Matlab. This is relevant it indicates that the awareness of the need of such practices is low amongs the latter group.

- Choosing which algorithm to implement is important to energy efficiency, as reducing the number of computational steps will also reduce the number of clock cycles on the processor. To gauge the importance of efficiency, we also want to know more generally how researchers choose which algorithms to implement.

Question: What are the main criteria you consider when selecting algorithms for your software? (for instance, high precision, short runtime, ease of implementation).

We received 8 answers, 2 from code optimisation experts:

- Depending on the research projects. Some aim for throughput, some for latency, some for power efficiency (expert).
- Short runtime
- Correctness, short runtime, parallelisability, ease of implementation
- fast and precise
- Ease of implementation
- It is my job to design them - so all of the above (expert).
- Short runtime, ease of implementation
- ease of implementation, short runtime

Short runtime was the most common factor when choosing algorithms at 5 of 8 responses, and ease of implementation a close second at 4 of 8 responses. No respondent cited energy efficiency, data storage size or memory size.

- Along with algorithms, the choice of data structures can also impact efficiency, although the data structure is often (not always) tied to the algorithm.

Question: What are the main criteria you consider when selecting data structures for your software? (for instance, high precision, short runtime, ease of implementation)

- Yes (expert).
- Easy, memory efficiency
- Low overhead, thread-safety, ease of implementation
- easy access and implementation
- It is my job to design them - so all of the above (expert).
- Ease of implementation in terms of input to the models.
- ease of implementation, short runtime

Researchers mostly favour ease of implementation when choosing data structures, at 5 of 7 responses, i.e. all except the HPC experts. As in the previous question, no respondent cited energy efficiency, data storage size or memory size.

- We asked if researchers are required to optimise their software before it is run on a facility, either local or national.

10 responses

Figure 8: Are you required to optimise the software before it is allowed to be run on the cluster/node?

The respondent who answered "yes" is not a user of local or national facilities. We can conclude that on the whole, there is no requirement to optimise software as a precondition for running on a cluster.

- Researchers are under pressure (internal and external) to produce results in their fields quickly. Among researchers who write code as part of their work, some have no assistance, while others have help from colleagues or computing specialists (such as research software engineers). Having access to this assistance could increase the efficiency of the research code. We included questions on these matters to get an overview of what researchers have available to them.

As figure 9 shows, 8 out of 11 respondents do not have access to help with optimisation.

11 responses

Figure 9: Do you have access to help to optimise the software you run on clusters/nodes?

Note that one respondent answered both 'Help from a knowledgeable colleague' and 'Help from a computing specialist', so a total of 2 respondents reported they have help.

The bottom response in figure 9 was a write-in as the respondent's work is researching efficiency in computing, so the question does not apply to their work. We conclude that the majority of non-expert users do not have access to help to optimise their software.

- The timeframe for getting feedback/help is important, researchers might need it quite quickly for it to be useful.

Question: How quickly do you need to have access to help for it to be useful? (for instance, so that it would be implemented before you run the software) (hours/days/months).

The responses were evenly split between hours, days and hours or days. The practical conclusion is that help should therefore be local rather than centralised.

- We asked the researchers about the confidence they have in their software's general energy efficiency. We chose to ask about confidence in this case, as a proper evaluation of optimisation is not feasible in our case, so their confidence is the closest measure we can gather at scale.

9 responses

Figure 10: How optimised do you think the software you have run on clusters/nodes is in terms of energy efficiency? (from 1="Not optimised" to 5="Highly optimised")

Among the 5 respondents who optimise their own software, 3 of 5 had a confidence of 3 in the energy efficiency of their software, and the other 2 responded 4 and 5. Response

5 is from the HPC expert. Among the 6 respondents who do not optimise their own software, 2 of 6 had a confidence of 3 in the energy efficiency of their software, 2 had a confidence of 1 (not optimised), and 2 did not respond. From the responses, we conclude that apart from the experts, the respondents' confidence in energy efficiency of their code is not high.

- To investigate which optimisation methods are being used in the field, we posed 3 confidence prompts on common avenues for software optimisation.

For parallel efficiency, we got an even spread in confidence.

- 4 of the 4 most confident (responded 4-5) optimised their own software.
 - * 1 of those 4 had support.
- 1 of the 4 least confident (responded 1-2) optimised their own software.
 - * None of those 4 had support.

9 responses

Figure 11: How confident are you in the parallel efficiency of your software? (from 1="Not optimised" to 5="Highly optimised")

For compiler optimisations, the respondents leaned toward low confidence.

- 3 of the 3 most confident (responded 3-5) optimise their own software.
 - * 1 of those 3 had support.
- 2 of the 6 least confident (responded 1-2) optimise their own software.
 - * None of those 6 had support.

9 responses

Figure 12: How confident are you in the compiler optimisations of your software? (from 1="Not optimised" to 5="Highly optimised")

For algorithm efficiency, the responses were evenly spread out.

- 4 of the 5 most confident (responded 4-5) optimised their own software.
 - * 1 of those 5 had support.
- 1 of the 4 least confident (responded 1-2) optimised their own software.
 - * None of those 4 had support.

10 responses

Figure 13: How confident are you in the efficiency of the algorithm(s) you've implemented? (from 1="Not optimised" to 5="Highly optimised")

From these results we conclude that on the whole, the respondents' confidence in the parallel efficiency, compiler optimisations and algorithm efficiency of their code is not high.

4.4.3 Unusable results / bugs

The purpose of this section is to build up a picture of the frequency of failed/incorrect experiments and the practices to reduce or avoid this.

- Frequency of running code with unusable results

11 responses

Figure 14: How often do you run software on a cluster/node you later discovered contained a bug or other flaw which led to a result that wholly or partially could not be used? (from 1="Never" to 5="All the time")

The responses of 1/Never in figure 14 is from a researcher who does not write their own code. The responses in figure 14 are evenly spread, so most of these researchers run experiments yielding unusable results on a regular basis.

- Which mitigating practices are currently employed in the field.

Note that in figure 15, "Run software on smaller sample" is the equivalent of "Manual testing" within software engineering.

10 responses

Figure 15: Which of the following procedures do you have to ensure software is correct before running it on a cluster/node?

With 1 respondent answering 'Not applicable', all the remaining respondents are running their software on smaller samples. This type of testing is more expensive than the other options in terms of computation, but it should catch some mistakes.

6 researchers responded that they used code reviews, but it should be noted that all but one of these respondents had previously stated they do not have help from a computing specialist or knowledgeable colleague in the question from figure 18. As none of them have filled in any alternatives, it is possible that they misinterpreted the meaning of "code reviews".

Note that the respondent who answered with the fill-in "Not guidance regarding software engineering practices" also ticked every other option for this question.

So overall, most researchers run small-scale experiments to debug their code, but other Software Engineering practices (code review, model review, unit testing, integration testing) are much less common.

- Researchers' perception of the effectiveness of these practices, and whether certain practices catches more mistakes than others:

9 responses

Figure 16: Do these procedures prevent results that cannot be used? (from 1="Never" to 5="Always")

Overall, the perception is that software engineering practices do help catch mistakes. Additionally, we found that:

- 2 of the 2 least effective measures (responded 1-2) did not respond with code reviews or unit testing among their practices.
 - * Both of the 2 did cite manual testing, and 1 cited integration testing.
- 4 of the 4 most effective measures (4-5) all cited code reviews, unit testing, and manual testing

So the perception of the respondents who use a more comprehensive set of practices is more strongly that those practices help, than those who only use limited testing.

- Are these practices enforced before researchers can run their software on facilities?

10 responses

Figure 17: Are you required to perform these procedures before the software is allowed to be run on the cluster/node?

In this case, only 1 researcher stated they are required to have employed these practices before they can run their software on facilities. This respondent is a user of the ARCHER2 supercomputer. 2 responded that they are not sure, but it would be reasonable to assume that if they are running software on facilities somewhere that requires it, they would know about it. That is, if it is required, they would not be allowed to run their software on the facility without proving they had used the practices. So we can conclude that the majority of researchers is not required to demonstrate use of a set of testing and review practices before deploying their code.

- Do researchers have support to help with software engineering practices?

10 responses

Figure 18: Do you have access to a computing specialist who can review your code for bugs?

Removing the 1 respondent who themselves are the computing experts, 8 out of the 10 researchers have no support available to help them review their software.

4.5 Survey Analysis Summary

4.5.1 Computing equipment

Overall, because of the small number of respondents, we can't draw any clear conclusions about the use of institutional computing facilities, personal devices and communal workstations, other than that they are broadly in line with the picture we obtained from the interviews and our inventory work.

4.5.2 Software efficiency

Languages and libraries The majority of users used Python (predominantly) or Matlab or R. C/C++ is also widely used. The lack of Fortran points to incomplete coverage due to small number of respondents. All Python users used high-performance libraries of some kind; R/Matlab users didn't.

Optimisation practices, support, and confidence We use the term "non-expert user" to indicate researchers whose expertise is not optimisation of code for energy efficiency, i.e. most researchers in UKRI.

- On the whole, non-expert users of Python, R and Matlab do not optimise their code; users of C/C++/C optimise their code.
- Optimisation practices are common for respondents who used C/C++/C but not for users of Python/R/Matlab. This is relevant as it indicates that the awareness of the need of such practices is low amongst the latter group.
- For most non-expert users, short runtime and ease of implementation are the key factors when choosing algorithms. No respondent cited energy efficiency, data storage size or memory size.
- For most non-expert users, ease of implementation was the key factor for choosing data structures. As in the previous question, no respondent cited energy efficiency, data storage size or memory size.
- On the whole, there is no requirement to optimise software as a precondition for running on a cluster.
- Most non-expert users do not have access to help with optimisation.
- The responses on the required timeframe for help were evenly split between hours, days and hours or days. The practical conclusion is that help should therefore be local rather than centralised.
- Non-expert users' confidence in energy efficiency of their code is not high.
- Non-expert users' confidence in the parallel efficiency, compiler optimisations and algorithm efficiency of their code is not high.

Unusable results

- Most non-expert users run experiments yielding unusable results on a regular basis.
- Most non-expert users run small-scale experiments to debug their code, but other Software Engineering practices (code review, model review, unit testing, integration testing) are much less common.

- The perception of non-expert users who use a more comprehensive set of practices is more strongly that those practices help, than those who only use limited testing.
- Most researchers are not required to demonstrate use of a set of testing and review practices before deploying their code.
- Most non-expert users have no support available to help them review their software.

4.6 Survey conclusions

The overall conclusions of the survey are:

4.6.1 Effectiveness of languages and code optimisation

- There's a lot of Python but mostly using high-performance libraries
- This is not the case for R and MatLab; Matlab has more potential for high performance but this is not within the capability of non-expert users. Typically, Python, R and Matlab users do not optimise their code.
- Although users of compiled code tend to optimise their programs, it is not clear how good these optimisations are.

4.6.2 Energy efficiency of algorithms and data structures

Based on the expressed priorities, algorithms and data structures are currently not selected for energy efficiency.

4.6.3 Confidence in energy efficiency of code

Non-expert users' confidence in energy, parallel efficiency, compiler optimisations and algorithm efficiency of their code is not high.

4.6.4 Requirements for optimisation of code

In general, there is no such requirement and therefore no assessment of performance.

4.6.5 Expert help

Most non-expert users do not have access to expert help for code optimisation. The required timeframe for such help would typically be hours, sometimes days.

4.7 Conclusions and Recommendations

4.7.1 General recommendation

Our general recommendation is that institutions should adopt the LEAF (Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework) for Digital Infrastructure.

4.7.2 Minimising full lifecycle emissions of institutional facilities

We recommend the following:

- Monitoring of facility load and coupling to replacement cycle: From our interviews we observed that the load for local facilities is often low. In such a regime, the embodied carbon of the hardware will dominate, so longer replacement cycles should be considered.
- Adopting access policies that incentives efficient time use of facilities and prevent squatting: From our interviews we observed that access policies such as first-come, first-serve can lead to "squatting", i.e. keeping resources occupied to avoid losing them. We recommend that appropriate access policies are put in place that discourage such practices.

4.7.3 Optimising code and reducing coding mistakes

From the interviews and surveys it is clear that (1) researchers realise that optimising code and reducing coding mistakes is important but (2) with the current model of incentivisations, they will not themselves invest time in this.

For deploying on controlled facilities, our recommendation is be to

- make the use of a workflow with testing and a transparent code review process mandatory.

This will greatly reduce deployment of buggy code and also reduce maintenance and debugging efforts and improve energy efficiency.

This will not help for more informal facilities, and it will also not help to address the issue of code optimisation. For that purposes, we would recommend

- Providing training on Software Engineering best practices:

Specifically, this should include:

- Principles of Green Software Design
- Code review: focus on energy efficiency of architecture, algorithms and implementation
- Testing: unit, integration and acceptance testing
- Use of build systems and revision control systems, in particular Continuous Integration workflows
- Compilation optimisation: use of compiler options to optimise energy efficiency
- Design of Experiments: ensure that the experiment produces the required results with minimal energy expenditure

The aim of this training is not to turn the researchers into software engineering or code optimisation experts. It is to provide researchers with teasy to acquire and apply knowledge and skills that will already greatly improve the overall energy efficiency of their digital experiments.

- Offering researchers expert support in the form of either
 - Research Software Engineers or
 - volunteer researchers trained to be experts.

Either way, these should be embedded in the researchers' departments, ideally even in their research groups. The role of these experts would on the one hand be code optimisation and on the other hand, assistance with implementation of Software Engineering best practices, including code review.

- Ensure adequate training of experts, specifically:
 - Code review for energy efficiency
 - Green Software Engineering practices
 - Code energy efficiency evaluation and optimisation
 - Compilation optimisation for energy efficiency
 - Design of Experiments optimisation for energy efficiency

The training of expert software engineers and programmers does currently not focus on energy efficiency and green practices.

Appendix: Limitations and lessons learned

Small sample size

The survey was distributed in 2 ways: appended to an e-mail going to a mailing list from another team within the consortium, and individually sent to researchers working for universities in the UK. In order to send these individual e-mails, we looked through staff directories of universities, and then checked the research interests section (where available) to confirm they were involved in digital research. The e-mail also encouraged distribution by the recipients, and was sent to over 100 researchers. Both these approaches combined resulted in 11 responses. The small sample size limits the strength of our conclusions, prevented some conclusions from being made, and does not allow for the use of statistical analysis. Researchers planning to extend this work, or perform similar work, should account for the effort needed to get a higher sample size.

Insufficient information on institutional facilities

One of the goals of the survey was to gather information about institutional level facilities, as there is not an overview of all the clusters running within universities. Although the we asked for descriptions of these facilities within the 'Institutional computing facilities' section, respondents mostly described either national level facilities, standalone workstations, or both. In this case, adding additional descriptions of what we were asking for could have improved the desired responses. For instance, we could say that the facilities in question was wholly owned and operated by their university, and were not standalone workstations as they would be covered later in the survey.

Ambiguous responses

As noted in the survey results section, there was a seeming contradiction between respondents claiming the practice of code reviews and not having support from knowledgeable colleagues or computing specialists. We speculate that this could come from a misunderstanding of the software engineering terms used. Code reviews could be interpreted as reviewing your own code for potential errors, whereas the software engineering term specifically requires the review to be done by another person. Similarly, integration testing could be interpreted as manually testing if segments of code (functions/member functions) work correctly when used in combination - as opposed to by themselves (unit testing). In that case, manual testing could also mean integration testing to respondents, but our intent was only to ask about automated integration testing. This situation could have been improved by adding descriptions of the specific terms used in the survey. Assuming either existing knowledge of these terms, or that researchers would look them up for a short survey, can make the results hard to interpret correctly.

Filter question

In the section filtering for writers/runners software for the purposes of experiments, the descriptive test includes this statement: "If your response to both the below questions are no, you do not need to complete the rest of the questionnaire.". However, the questions about personal devices were positioned later in the survey. These were responses we wished to capture regardless of the filter, so the questions on personal devices should have been covered before the filter section, or at least the statement that they would not need to complete the remaining questions. As we did not receive any responses which had stopped answering questions at this point, it does not appear to have affected our results.